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<https://doi.org/10.61796/ejheaa.v1i7.722>**IMPLEMENTATION OF LEARNING MANAGEMENT
AT DARUL AMAN ISLAMIC BOARDING SCHOOL OF
ACEH BESAR DISTRICT****Miswar**

STAI Tgk. Chik Pante Kulu Banda Aceh, Indonesia

aceh_miswar@yahoo.com

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Abstract: Some teachers will complete the learning tool when there is a visit by the school supervisor to the pesantren and also when they complete it only to complete the requirements to receive the teacher's professional allowance. The results of the study are (1). The planning implications in the learning management at Darul Aman Islamic Boarding School of Aceh Besar District are proven by holding a teaching plan, because teaching planning is a very important matter arranged optimally before the learning process is implemented, whether or not the learning process is carried out well depending on the teaching plan that has been set together. Islamic Boarding School leaders as supervisors are able to guide and supervise teachers in preparing teaching plans. (2). The implementation implications in the learning management at Darul Aman Islamic Boarding School Of Aceh Besar District is the learning process is carried out with a). Manage the learning process, b). Manage classes, c). Using media, d). Mastery of the educational foundation, and e). Manage learning interactions. (3). The implications of controlling in the learning management at Darul Aman Islamic Boarding School of Aceh Besar District are carried out by evaluating the weaknesses and programs that have been implemented to improve the implementation of the program to improve future learning. Control is carried out in the provision of reports carried out and discussed together.

Keywords: Implementation, Learning Management, Islamic Boarding School

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Introduction

The teaching and learning process in simple terms can be interpreted as an activity of interaction and mutual influence between educators and students, with the main function of education providing subject matter or something that influences students, while students receive lessons, influence or something given by educators. And the verses of the Qur'an can be obtained cues about teaching and learning activities with various components. in surah al alaq (96) verses 1 to 5, the teaching and learning process takes place from God to the prophet Muhammad SAW. Through the method of reading (iqra') God (through the angel Gabriel) wants the prophet Muhammad SAW to read everything that was conveyed by the angel Gabriel (Nata, 2010: 141).

In a broader and systematic sense, the teaching and learning process is an activity that involves a number of components that are one and the other. These components include the vision and goals to be achieved, teachers who are professional and ready to teach, students who are ready to receive lessons, approaches to be used, strategies to be implemented, methods to be chosen, techniques and tactics to be used. Thus, the measure of the success of a teaching and learning process can be seen in the extent to which the

process is able to grow, foster, shape, and empower all human potentials, or to what extent it is able to provide significant changes to the participants' cognitive, affective and psychomotor abilities students (Nata, 2010: 143).

Islamic boarding schools as the forerunner of original Indonesian education only received juridical recognition in 2003 through National Education System Law no. 20 of 2003. At the beginning of Indonesian independence, the Working Committee of the Central Indonesian National Committee, which acted as a parliamentary institution at that time, in its recommendation points on 27 December 1945 concerning educational reform, among other things, suggested that madrasas and Islamic boarding schools In essence, it is a tool and source of education in the education of ordinary people who are already ingrained in Indonesian society in general, should also receive real attention and assistance in the form of guidance and material assistance from the government (Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia, 2003: 13).

According to Mastuhu, the aim of the Islamic boarding school learning program is to create a Muslim personality, namely a personality that is faithful and devoted to God, has noble character, is beneficial to the community or is wise to the community by becoming subjects or serving the community, able to stand alone, free and firm in personality, spread religion or uphold Islam and the glory of Muslims in the midst of society and love of knowledge in order to develop Indonesian personality. Ideally the personality development you want to aim for is the mukhsin personality, not just a Muslim (Masyhud & Khusnurdilo, 2003: 92-93).

In preparing development human resources, learning programs cannot only focus on material needs but must touch the base to give character to the vision and mission of education, namely deep attention to noble moral and spiritual ethics. In this case the quality of education is influenced by all components of education such as quality improvement and equity in the distribution of teachers, adequate infrastructure, a conducive learning climate, and supported by government policies, both at the central and regional levels. Of all that, the teacher is the most decisive component, because it is in the hands of the teacher that the curriculum, learning resources, facilities and infrastructure, and the learning climate become something meaningful for the lives of students. Human life cannot be separated from values, and these values need to be institutionalized. The best institution is through educational efforts. The existence of Islamic boarding schools and their devices as Islamic institutions, of course, has distinctive values that distinguish them from other educational institutions. In reality, Islamic boarding school values developed by Islamic boarding schools are rooted in divine values and human values (Mansur, 2004: 55).

From the results of temporary observations, that the Darul Aman Islamic Boarding School Of Aceh Besar District, in recent years, through the leadership of the existing Head of Madrasah, has not yet begun to make changes to improve teacher professionalism. This indication arises from the failure of the Darul Aman Islamic Boarding School of Aceh Besar District in producing graduates, with average UAN scores and an average pass rate of 75%. The students at Darul Aman Islamic Boarding School of Aceh Besar District, consist of students who have transferred from other schools. In general, almost 80% of those accepted there are students who have family problems and from other schools before they moved to the Darul Aman Islamic Boarding School of Aceh Besar District, so students rarely complete

their learning needs, such as textbooks, stationery and so on. On the other hand there are also teachers who have achievements in their fields and the increasing interest of teachers to further improve their professionalism, for example the desire to improve education, follow include training, and study quality textbooks / science. However, they easily resign and teach at other schools, plus they are sometimes rarely present in the learning process.

Methods

This type of research is qualitative, qualitative research is a type of research that produces findings that cannot be achieved using statistical procedures or other quantification methods. The data source is divided into two parts, namely the primary data source, namely the teachers. Secondary data sources are supporting data related to this research, namely school principals, students and components that researchers consider to be related to the implications of pesantren management. To dig up information and get data from data sources, a snow ball sampling technique was used in which more informants could be added as needed until valid data was obtained.

Data collection techniques are carried out by observation, interviews and documentation studies. Data analysis was carried out using two methods, namely quantitative and qualitative. The data that has been collected, analyzed descriptively qualitatively. Clearly, the data collected is analyzed inductively at any time during the research by processing empirical material, so that it can be simplified into a form that is easier to read, understand, and interpret. Data is interpreted to find meaning and implementation of existing relationships.

Testing the validity of the data can be done by extending observations, increasing persistence in research, triangulation, discussions with colleagues, negative case analysis, and member checks. Validity and Reliability Qualitative research. At the initial stage of entering the field, researchers are still considered foreigners, they are still suspected, so the information provided is incomplete, not in-depth, and perhaps much is still kept secret. By extending this observation, the researcher re-checked whether the data provided so far was correct or not. If the data that has been obtained so far after checking back on the original data source or other data sources is not correct, the researcher will make further observations more broadly and in-depth to obtain data that is definitely correct. The length of time this extension of the observation is carried out depends heavily on the depth, breadth, and certainty of the data.

Results and Discussion

1. Implementation of Planning in Learning Management at Darul Aman Islamic Boarding School of Aceh Besar District

plan is very important to be prepared as optimally as possible before the learning process is carried out, whether or not the learning process is carried out properly depends on the teaching plan. Therefore, Islamic Boarding School Leaders as supervisors are able to guide and supervise teachers in preparing teaching plans. The guidance given by the Board of

Islamic Boarding Schools to teachers in preparing teaching plans is carried out at the beginning of each semester or at the beginning of each semester through special meetings. In the meeting the teachers were briefed on all matters relating to the learning process, including:

- a. Teaching planning
- b. Teaching management
- c. Learning evaluation
- d. Constraints and obstacles experienced by teachers in the learning process.
- e. Implementation of remedial teaching and enrichment.

Planning is a number of activities that are predetermined for carried out in a certain period in order to achieve that goal set. Planning is a process Prepare systematic activities that will be carried out to achieve certain goals. Planning is also a calculation and determination of something to be executed in order to achieve specific goals, about who does it, when, where, and how do it. Siagian defines planning as a whole process thought And careful determination things Which will be done in the future in order to achieve the goals that have been predetermined. Y. Dior argues that the so-called planning is a process of preparing a set of decisions to be implemented on the future, which is directed to achieve certain goals. From the above understanding, it can be concluded that the so-called (Usman, 2006: 48) . Planning is an activity that will be carried out in the future to reach the goal. From here planning contains elements, namely:

- a. predetermined number of activities
- b. there is a process
- c. results to be achieved
- d. concerning the future at a certain time Planning cannot be separated from the elements of implementation and supervision monitoring, assessment, and reporting. Supervision of supervision in planning can be done in a preventive and repressive manner.

Preventive supervision is supervision that is attached to its planning , while repressive supervision is supervision Functional for the implementation of the plan, both carried out internally as well as externally by the assigned supervisory apparatus (Usman, 2006: 49). Thus educational planning is a decision taken to take action for a certain time (in accordance with the planning period) so that the implementation of the education system becomes more effective and efficient, and produces graduates who are of higher quality, and are relevant to development needs (Fattah, 1996: 50)

In the planning process for educational programs to be implemented, especially in Islamic educational institutions, the planning principles must reflect Islamic values that are rooted in the Al-Qur'an and al-Hadith. This verse is a very principled thing that is not negotiable in the educational planning process, so that the goals to be achieved can be achieved perfectly. Besides that, the essence of the verse is a differentiator between management in general and management in an Islamic perspective which is full of values.

Learning management contains meaning as a process of systematic, systemic, and comprehensive cooperation in order to realize the goals of national education. Learning management can also be interpreted as everything related to the management of the educational process to achieve the goals that have been set, both short-term, medium-term and long-term goals. According to E. Mulyasa management learning is the process of developing cooperative activities of a group of people to achieve predetermined educational goals. The process of controlling these activities includes planning, organizing, actuating and controlling, as a process to turn vision into action (Mulyasa, 2004: 19-20).

Learning management is the art and science of managing educational resources to create a learning atmosphere and learning process students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and the skills needed by himself, society, the nation and the State (Usman, 2006: 7).

It can also be interpreted that learning management is also a series joint activities or the entire process of business control over cooperation. A group of people in achieving predetermined educational goals in a planned and systematic manner, which is held in an environment In particular, education management is essentially related to educational goals, people who collaborate, systemic and systematic processes, and resources that are utilized (Mulyasa, 2004: 9).

2. Implementation of Implementation in Learning Management at the Darul Aman Islamic Boarding School of Aceh Besar District

implementation stage is the core stage of the teaching and learning process. In this implementation stage, various teacher abilities are needed so that the teaching and learning process is carried out as it should. The things that should be done by the teacher when carrying out the learning process include:

- a. Open the lesson properly, so that students' interest in following the teaching and learning process is maintained
- b. Conducting classroom management, so that the classroom situation runs as well as possible.

- c. Provide an explanation of the material as best as possible, so that students can understand the material presented
- d. Ask students about the material presented, so that this becomes a reference for the teacher to continue on to the material.
- e. Using the method according to the subject matter
- f. Use teaching media when necessary.

Based on interviews with the Board of Directors of the Islamic Boarding School, among the things that are the object of supervision of the Leadership of the Darul Aman Islamic Boarding School of Aceh Besar District in carrying out the learning process can be stated as follows:

- a. Manage the learning process, including:
 - 1) Formulate instructional objectives
 - 2) Recognize and be able to use teaching methods
 - 3) Select and structure appropriate instructional procedures
 - 4) Carry out learning programs
 - 5) Get to know the abilities of students
 - 6) Plan and implement remedial
- b. Manage classes

Organize classroom layout for teaching

Creating a harmonious learning climate

- c. using media
 - 1) Recognize, select and use media
 - 2) Make learning aids that are simple
 - 3) Using and managing the laboratory within the framework of the learning process
 - 4) Develop laboratory
 - 5) Using the library in the learning process
- d. Mastery of the educational foundation
 - 1) a sociological, philosophical, historical and psychological perspective

- 2) Recognize the function of madrasas as social institutions that can potentially advance society in a broad sense and the mutual influence between madrasas and society
- e. Manage learning interactions
- 1) Learn ways to motivate students to learn
 - 2) Using ways to motivate students
 - 3) Learn the different types of questions
 - 4) Study some of the psychological mechanisms of learning
 - 5) Examine the positive and negative factors in the learning process
 - 6) Learn ways of interpersonal communication
 - 7) Using interpersonal communication methods.

Learning management goals are closely related to educational goals general, because educational management is essentially a tool for achieve educational goals optimally. When it comes to understanding Educational management is essentially a means to an end. The goal of national education is to develop potential students to become human beings who believe and fear God the one and only, noble, healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become a democratic and responsible citizen. The main purpose of studying educational management is to get the best ways, techniques, methods, so that the resources. Which is very limited such as manpower, funds, facilities, material and spiritual in order to achieve educational goals effectively and efficiently (National Education System Law No. 20 of 2003: 7)

According to Shrode and Voich (1974) the main objective of educational management is productivity and satisfaction. Maybe this goal is not singular or even plural or double, such as improving the quality of education/graduates, profit/profit high, fulfillment of regional/national development job opportunities, social responsibility. These goals are determined based on structuring and assessment of the situation and condition of the organization, such as strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats (Fattah, 1996: 15).

Based on the technical understanding, productivity can be measured by two main standards, namely physical productivity and value productivity. Physically, productivity is measured quantitatively, such as the number of outputs (length, weight, length of time, quantity). Meanwhile, based on value, productivity is measured on the basics of the values of ability, attitude, behavior, discipline, motivation, and commitment to work/task (Fattah, 1996: 15).

In detail the objectives of learning management include:

- a. Creating an active, creative, effective and fun learning atmosphere and learning process (PAKEM)
- b. The creation of students who actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and skills needed by themselves, society, nation and state
- c. Achievement of educational goals effectively and efficiently
- d. Provision of educational staff with theories about the processes and tasks of educational administration
- e. Overcoming the problem of quality of education (Usman, 2006: 8).

activities are a condition that is deliberately created. Teaching is the activity of conveying messages in the form of knowledge, skills and cultivating certain attitudes from the teacher to students. Understanding teaching as the creation of an environmental system that allows the learning process to occur. The environmental system in the learning process will influence each other between components such as instructional goals to be achieved, teachers and students who play similar roles in certain social relations, the material being taught, the forms of activities carried out and the available teaching and learning facilities and infrastructure.

So teaching and learning is a process of interaction between students and teachers regarding the transfer of knowledge, values and attitudes in educational activities in the classroom. The role of the teacher as a guide departs from many problematic students. In learning there are students who are quick to accept lessons, some are moderate and some are slow to accept lessons. These three types of student learning require the teacher to arrange teaching strategies that are in accordance with the learning styles of students. Finally, if the nature of learning is change then teaching is a regulatory process carried out by the teacher

As a process of teaching and learning arrangements cannot be separated from certain characteristics, which according to Edi Suardi are as follows:

- a. Teaching and learning has a goal, namely to form students in a certain development.
- b. There is a planned procedure, designed to achieve a predetermined goal
- c. Teaching and learning activities are characterized by the cultivation of a special material.
- d. There are student activities
- e. In teaching and learning activities the teacher acts as a guide
- f. In teaching and learning activities it takes discipline
- g. There is a time limit

As a system, of course teaching and learning activities contain a number of components which include the objectives of teaching and learning activity materials, methods, tools and sources as well as evaluation. Teaching and learning activities are the core activities in education. Everything that is programmed will be carried out in the teaching and learning process. In teaching and learning activities, teachers and students are involved in an interaction with the subject matter as the medium. In this activity students are guided to be active in the learning process so that the material presented can be accepted by students. The method is a method that is used to achieve the goals that have been set. In teaching and learning activities required by the teacher and usage varies according to the objectives to be achieved. The use of the right method will affect the learning process and the goals to be achieved at the end of the learning process.

learning process can involve cognitive, affective and psychomotor aspects. In cognitive learning, the process results in changes in aspects of thinking ability (cognitive), in affective learning results in changes in aspects of feeling (affective) abilities, while psychomotor learning provides learning outcomes in the form of skills (psychomotoric). The learning process is unique and complex. This uniqueness is caused by learning outcomes only in individuals who learn, not in other people, and each individual displays different learning behavior. The difference in appearance is because each individual has unique individual characteristics, such as interest, intelligence, attention, talent and so on. Every human being has a unique way of making the learning process happen within him. Different individuals can carry out the learning process with different abilities in cognitive, affective and psychomotor aspects. Likewise, the same individual has different abilities in learning cognitive, affective and psychomotor aspects (Purwanto, 2009: 42-43).

3. Implementation of Control in Learning Management at Darul Aman Islamic Boarding School of Aceh Besar District

At the Darul Aman Islamic Boarding School of Aceh Besar District, the role of mentor teachers and other teachers in controlling the programs made by the pesantren leadership is very important. Because of the implementation of activities, of course there will be obstacles. Like child discipline, motivation to run this honesty program. All need guidance and direction from coaches and teacher councils. So that from the good cooperation shown by the teacher assembly through the activity program set by the pesantren leadership, it can be synergized with programs created to improve learning at the Darul Aman Islamic Boarding School of Aceh Besar District.

The leadership of the pesantren conducts meetings at least once a month in the teacher's room provided by the pesantren foundation. And in these meetings always evaluate the

activities carried out and will be carried out under the guidance of the supervising teacher. Because the role of the supervising teacher is highly expected when they encounter problems in carrying out the program. The mentor teacher helps the pesantren leadership, from program planning to the evaluation process and helps communicate the source of activity funds to the pesantren leadership .

Control and Evaluation is carried out to see weaknesses and programs that have been implemented in order to improve program implementation to improve learning in the future. Control is carried out in the provision of reports which are carried out and discussed jointly. Evaluation of Islamic religious education learning is a very important factor for measuring the level of students' understanding of Islamic education theoretically. This is very important to do so that the results obtained become a guide and reference for teachers in carrying out the learning process of Islamic education in the future. The form of cooperation between the madrasah and the parents of students is by holding a friendly gathering with the parents of students ahead of the students' school holidays. In this case the madrasa held communication and question and answer with parents of students about various child developments in the madrasa. Furthermore, the madrasa asked the parents of students to supervise and guide intensively in the midst of the community.

The implementation of the evaluation of Islamic education learning at the Darul Aman Islamic Boarding School of Aceh Besar District is not only carried out through written exams. However, it is also carried out intensively both through direct observation in daily life in the madrasa environment and through daily tests given by religious teachers. The pesantren leaders who were interviewed stated that the pesantren leaders asked religion teachers to evaluate Islamic religious education learning not only through written exams, because written exams are only assessments that reveal students' cognitive aspects. However, the Board of Islamic Boarding Schools requested that the religious teacher conduct an assessment of the students' psychomotor skills both through behavior, words and deeds in everyday life, especially in the madrasah environment.

Supervision is an activity that strives for work can be carried out in accordance with the plans or objectives that have been set. In other words, supervision is an assessment As well as corrections so that what has been planned can be implemented correctly (Fattah, 1996: 99). According to M udrick supervision is a fundamental process that e sensi is still needed no matter how complex and extensive an organization is. The basic process consists of three stages:

- a. Determine performance standards,
- b. Measurement of work performance compared to standards

- c. Determine the gap (deviation) between implementation and standards and plans.

In the supervision process there are at least three phases that must be passed in this supervision, namely:

- a. Leaders must determine or set standards,
- b. Evaluation
- c. Corrective action, namely carrying out corrective actions with the intention that the monitoring objectives can be realized. While the main purpose of this pengawan is to make things right planned to come true or can be realized.

Controlling is important because it is the final bridge in the functional chain of management activities. Control is one way for managers to find out whether organizational goals are achieved or not and why they are achieved or not achieved. Besides that, controlling is a control concept, monitoring the effectiveness of planning, organizing, and leadership as well as making improvements when needed.

In learning, the process of controlling and evaluating is done by research. Formative assessments need to be carried out for improvements whose implementation can be carried out with the following procedures:

- a. Develop ways to assess student learning outcomes.
- b. Use the results of the assessment to analyze the weaknesses or deficiencies of students and the problems faced by teachers in building the character and competence of students.

Choose the most appropriate methodology according to the competence to be achieved. (Mulyasa, 2004: 102-103).

Conclusion

The implications of planning in the learning management of the Darul Aman Islamic Boarding School of Aceh Besar District are proven by conducting teaching plans, because teaching planning is very important to be prepared as optimally as possible before the learning process is carried out, whether or not the learning process is carried out properly depends on the teaching plan that has been determined together. Pesantren leaders as supervisors are able to guide and supervise teachers in preparing teaching plans. The implication of implementation in learning management at Darul Aman Islamic Boarding School of Aceh Besar District in the learning process is carried out by 1). Manage the learning process, 2). Manage class, 3). Using the media, 4). Mastery of the educational foundation, and 5). Manage learning interactions. The implications of controlling in the learning management of Darul Aman Islamic Boarding School Of Aceh Besar District, are carried out by conducting evaluations to see weaknesses and programs that have been implemented to improve program implementation to improve learning in the future. Control is carried out in the provision of reports that are carried out and discussed jointly.

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